

D5.1 Report on the tension between FAIR guiding principles and sensitive data

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ALLEA. All European Academies

DMP. Data Management Plan

EOSC. European Open Science Cloud

EU. European Union

FAIR. Findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable

GDPR. General Data Protection Regulation

IPR. Intellectual property rights

ORD. Open Research Data

SRIA. Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda

UDHR. Universal Declaration of Human Rights

UNECE. United Nations Economic Commission for Europe

1 INTRODUCTION

While there is a consensus in the scientific community on the importance of data 'FAIRness' (Jacobsen *et al*, 2020), there is also a common understanding that the collection, management and disclosure of scientific data and metadata raises legal, social and ethical issues. SIESTA project WP5, entitled "Frictionless FAIR sensitive data", faces this twofold topic, being its main objective to provide "a map of the interaction between the 15 FAIR principles and sensitive data, analysing the applicability of the principles to the different grades of data sensitiveness and its metadata". Specifically, WP5 Task 5.1 describes its ambition as follows: "The 15 FAIR principles are different in their capacity of intrusiveness in disclosing sensitive data. Therefore, an initial analysis is needed in order to identify in what terms each of the 15 FAIR principles may be in tension with third parties rights over the data. The method of the analysis will consist of, considering the rule of 'as open as possible, as closed as necessary' where openness is the rule, the delimitations of the exceptions brought by the content of the data or the rights over it. The aim is to deliver a useful map of the interplay between each FAIR principle and the variables that may hinder it, mainly privacy and intellectual property rights over the data, providing solutions for the necessary balance between the FAIR principles and the protection of citizen rights."

The outcome of the works done within WP5 T5.1 is documented in this Deliverable 5.1, "Report on the tension between FAIR guiding principles and sensitive data", which contains the analysis of the relationship between the 15 FAIR guiding principles and the different parameters that could affect their openness.

2 METHODOLOGY

The context of the FAIR guiding principles (Wilkinson *et al*, 2016) was conceptualized by the European Commission Expert Group on FAIR Data in their report “Turning FAIR into reality. Final Report and Action Plan from the European Commission Expert Group on FAIR Data” (European Commission, 2018). The report considered the existence of two elements that needed a holistic study and that could not be analysed separately: On one side, FAIR digital objects, which “could represent data, software, protocols or other research resources” and, on the other, the FAIR ecosystem which comprises “services and infrastructures for FAIR”. The holistic methodology used by the report was imposed by its purpose of describing “the broad range of changes required to turn FAIR data into reality”. To create this reality, FAIR Digital Objects needed to be “accompanied by Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) and metadata rich enough to enable them to be reliably found, used and cited” sitting, as per the report wording, “in a wider FAIR ecosystem” at a minimum composed by “policies, DMPs, identifiers, standards and repositories”. In this ecosystem, “data policies are issued by several stakeholders and help to define and regulate requirements for the running of data services”.

The subsequent steps of “turning FAIR into reality”, which have been the creation of the EOSC, the design and implementation of the first version of the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) (European Commission, 2022), and the further studies and attainments made by EOSC projects, provided an analytical approach based on the singular components of the FAIR ecosystem. In this younger stage, FAIR concepts are being deeply studied and services and tools are being developed. In this step, the reports, studies and deliverables’ methodological approach is no longer a top-down holistic view, but in many cases it focuses on the different pieces of the ecosystem. This is the method chosen in SIESTA project WP5, where it has been deemed necessary to study one by one the 15 components of the FAIR guiding principles and their relationship with the opposition open/closed.

The analysis starts with a conceptual study of the expression “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”, which has acquired an extensive usage in different texts around the world, determining the default openness and the possible legal, social and ethical elements that could hinder it. Once the opposition between the default openness and

the exceptional closeness is framed, each of the 15 guiding principles is confronted to the open/close contrast, providing the relevant issues that may appear.

In the FAIR ecosystem, interoperability is a core component which needs semantic technologies in order to ensure it being machine actionable. Hence, to foster such a component, the result of the open/close opposition should be incorporated into a limited vocabulary list where the terms that play a role in the tension would be enumerated, described and categorised. The terms could use as their definition the wording included in the legal texts, if such legal definition existed. Even though this aspect is out of the scope of this deliverable, some initial steps for arriving at a result are included.

Finally, a short reference of the peculiarities of SIESTA's use cases will be documented, following the lessons learnt during the project.

3 AS OPEN AS POSSIBLE, AS CLOSED AS NECESSARY

The expression “As open as possible, as closed as necessary” is currently a common place in the research domain, although little has been done in the scientific literature to fully study its boundaries. In 2022, this expression merited one section of the report mandated by the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation of the European Commission entitled “Open Science and Intellectual Property Rights. How can they better interact? State of the art and reflections” (European Commission, 2022). Section 6 of the report, entitled “Scope of ‘as open as possible, as closed as necessary’”, included what was an extensive analysis of the expression, based on a first general rule, the necessity of openness of scientific activity in order to be considered Science as such, and two exceptions where not disclosing the information would be reasonably allowed: the first exception due to the content of the information and the second due to the rights over it.

In the European Union, the expression has consolidated its importance since its initial documented appearance in the specifications of the 2016 pilot ORD (Open Research Data). According to this document, “In the 2014-16 work programmes, the ORD pilot included only selected areas of Horizon 2020. Under the revised version of the 2017 work programme, the Open Research Data pilot has been extended to cover all the thematic areas of Horizon 2020.” (European Commission, 2016). The aim of the ORD pilot was “to improve and maximise access to and re-use of research data generated by Horizon 2020 projects”, not forgetting “the need to balance openness and protection of scientific information, commercialisation and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), privacy concerns, security as well as data management and preservation questions”. As literally expressed in this document (p. 4):

Participating in the ORD Pilot does not necessarily mean opening up all your research data. Rather, the ORD pilot follows the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” and focuses on encouraging sound data management as an essential part of research best practice.

The expression “As open as possible, as closed as necessary” could afterwards be found worded as “as open as possible, and only as closed as necessary” in the First draft of

the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (UNESCO, 2020). The final text of the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (UNESCO, 2021) dropped the “as closed as necessary” part, leaving it as “Access to scientific knowledge should be as open as possible”. The expression is demonstrating that it is not a void set of words, but that it has practical implications. Specific examples of the “openness” of scientific activities are described in the “Open science outlook 1: status and trends around the world” (UNESCO, 2023), where details of 23 examples of “Open Science in action” can be found. The examples relate to infrastructures (avoiding duplication, enhance inclusion and publishing), to open software, to FAIR guiding principles (increase traceability of research through PIDs and global cooperation on policy and practice for interoperability), to skills, to publishing scientific outcomes (open repositories, protecting researchers from predatory behaviours), to national frameworks or policies (Finland, South Africa, Netherlands and CERN), to fostering practices in early careers and institutions, to research assessment, and to funding.

Both adjectives *open* and *closed* are polysemous and admit legal and colloquial meanings. Free culture and free software movements have made an effort to define their semantic content. The Open Knowledge Foundation, building on top of “the Open Source Definition, which in turn was derived from the original Debian Free Software Guidelines, and the Debian Social Contract of which they are a part”² proposed the “Open Definition. Defining Open in Open Data, Open Content and Open Knowledge”³, summarising its understanding as follows: “Open data and content can be freely used, modified, and shared by anyone for any purpose”. The Open Source Definition⁴, the Debian Free Software Guidelines⁵, the Free Software Foundation⁶ and Creative Commons⁷ arrive at a common interpretation, which is that a work is *open* when it is *free* to be used, considering openness and closeness not a binary opposite pair but a gradient. In all cases, their understanding is based on intellectual property laws and therefore colloquial uses of *open* and *closed* are not taken into consideration. In accordance with this interpretation, even though a book is readable, thus its text is open to be known, its

² See <https://opendefinition.org/od/2.1/en/>

³ See <https://opendefinition.org/>

⁴ See <https://opensource.org/osd>

⁵ See https://www.debian.org/social_contract

⁶ See <https://www.gnu.org/philosophy/free-sw.html.en>

⁷ See <https://creativecommons.org/public-domain/freeworks/>

readability would not mean that it is an open work. Due to the understanding of the *open* being based in intellectual property law, the consent of the rightholder would be a central piece of this construct. Nevertheless, in this deliverable we will take into consideration closeness not only dependent on intellectual property rights, but also due to social and ethical reasons. As closed as necessary may respond to more reasons than the mere legal ones.

It is also worth mentioning that the perspective presented in this deliverable is a global one. Even though intellectual property rights offer a very hierarchical regulation with international treaties conveying what is then developed in national laws, or even though in the EU privacy regulation is articulated through a single norm, the GDPR, every jurisdiction shows singularities that must be respected. Thus, the purpose of this analysis is a general one, a bird's eye view that can serve for the maximum number of possible cases.

Lastly, to understand the internal logic of the expression it is convenient to explain the well established legal distinction between what is known as *absolute* and *qualified rights*. While *absolute rights* do not allow any exception, *qualified rights* allow interference subject to various conditions and must be interpreted and applied in balance with other rights. Examples of *absolute rights* are the interdiction of torture, slavery, imprisonment for inability to fulfil a contractual obligation, the retrospective operation of criminal laws and the right to recognition before the law. An example of *qualified right*, is the right to science. It is in the context of bringing to data management the application of a *qualified right* that we must study the expression "as open as possible, as closed as necessary", first by understanding why scientific data should be open (as open as possible), and second, by enumerating and describing what elements could interfere with the openness, obliging data not be disclosed (as closed as necessary).

3.1 AS OPEN AS POSSIBLE

3.1.1 The right of access to public information

By default, citizens in a democratic society have the right to access public information (public organisations' records). Well educated citizens' participation⁸, transparent organisations and accountability of public institutions form democracy's main pillars. For this to happen, openness of information is a necessary requirement. These elements underpinned the creation and conceptualization of Human Rights even before these norms were formalized in legal texts such as national constitutions and international treaties. Access to information, the right to know, is necessary to exercise the freedom of thought, conscience and religion established in article 18 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR). In addition, freedom of opinion and expression (article 19 UDHR) are built over the freedom of thought. The roots of these rights dig deep in occidental philosophy, being Kant's "Perpetual Peace: A Philosophical Sketch" (published in 1795) one of the relevant sources: "All maxims that require publicity (in order that they not miss their aim) are in agreement with both politics and right." (Kant 2006, p. 109). Therefore, there is a solid link that ties the chain composed by the right to know, freedom of thought and freedom of expression, with the foundations of a democratic system.

In our present times, these values persist. The Report of the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights States (UN, 2022) asserts that "States should promote the principles of openness and transparency in all aspects of decision-making processes, and of accountability of public authorities for the implementation of the right to participate in public affairs". According to the UN report, access to information is relevant under a political perspective, albeit "crucial for the promotion of personal autonomy" and, furthermore, "is instrumental for the enjoyment of a range of other human rights, such as the right to health" as the COVID pandemic demonstrated.

In order to create better normative frameworks that guarantee the access to public information, the UN report suggests, in its paragraph 15, five elements that would

⁸ There is a long tradition that finds a direct relationship between democratic quality and citizens' education. For a deeper insight, see <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/civic-education/>

provide a stronger access to information and a better accomplishment of the right to know:

The normative framework should be recognized by law, based on a principle of maximum disclosure, provide for proactive publication, incorporate procedures that facilitate access and include independent oversight and review. In addition, States should promote access to the Internet.

The ideas set forth in the before normative framework show strong analogies with the Open Science principles of finding and sharing scientific publications and data. The “maximum disclosure” principle is *mutatis mutandis* the application to public information of the expression “as open as possible”, while the proactive publication, the procedure to facilitate access and the promotion of Internet, fall under the recommendations for the Findability and Accessibility of the FAIR principles.

Regarding the EU, the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (the Charter) recognises the right of receiving information. Article 11, on Freedom of expression and information, asserts that “1. Everyone has the right to freedom of expression. This right shall include freedom to hold opinions and to receive and impart information and ideas without interference by public authority and regardless of frontiers”. Additionally, the Charter recognises in its article 42 the right of access to EU public bodies documents: “Any citizen of the Union, and any natural or legal person residing or having its registered office in a Member State, has a right of access to European Parliament, Council and Commission documents.” The regulation set forth in the Charter must be interpreted in accordance to the content of the Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information⁹, known as the Open Data Directive. The Directive establishes in its Whereas 5 that “Access to information is a fundamental right” and in its article 1 regulates what the EU member states must include in their national regulations. The Directive sets up the minimum requirements that the member states must include in their legislation. According to the Open Data Directive, citizens of the EU have the right to access to the following information:

⁹ See <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2019/1024/oj>

Article 1. Subject matter and scope

1. In order to promote the use of open data and stimulate innovation in products and services, this Directive establishes a set of minimum rules governing the re-use and the practical arrangements for facilitating the re-use of:
 - (a) Existing documents held by public sector bodies of the Member States;
 - (b) Existing documents held by public undertakings that are:
 - (i) Active in the areas defined in Directive 2014/25/EU (procurement by entities operating in the water, energy, transport and postal services sectors);
 - (ii) Acting as public service operators pursuant to Article 2 of Regulation (EC) No. 1370/2007 (public passenger transport services by rail and by road);
 - (iii) Acting as air carriers fulfilling public service obligations pursuant to Article 16 of Regulation (EC) No 1008/2008; or
 - (iv) Acting as Community shipowners fulfilling public service obligations pursuant to Article 4 of Regulation (EEC) No 3577/92;
 - (c) Research data pursuant to the conditions set out in Article 10.

What is of most interest for this deliverable is item c). Citizenship has the right to access Research data under the following conditions:

Article 10. Research data

1. Member States shall support the availability of research data by adopting national policies and relevant actions aiming at making publicly funded research data openly available ('open access policies'), following the principle of 'open by default' and compatible with the FAIR principles. In that context, concerns relating to intellectual property rights, personal data protection and confidentiality, security and legitimate commercial interests, shall be taken into

account in accordance with the principle of ‘as open as possible, as closed as necessary’. Those open access policies shall be addressed to research performing organisations and research funding organisations.

2. Without prejudice to point (c) of Article 1(2) [documents for which third parties hold intellectual property rights], research data shall be re-usable for commercial or non-commercial purposes in accordance with Chapters III and IV, insofar as they are publicly funded and researchers, research performing organisations or research funding organisations have already made them publicly available through an institutional or subject-based repository. In that context, legitimate commercial interests, knowledge transfer activities and pre-existing intellectual property rights shall be taken into account.

Finally, also regarding European countries, it is worth mentioning the Convention on Access to Information, Public Participation in Decision-making and Access to Justice in Environmental Matters. The text, known as the Aarhus Convention (UNECE, 1998), is an international instrument signed by the member states of the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE)¹⁰. The Preamble of Aarhus Convention recognises the right of access to information, recognition that is specified in article 4 of the text, on the Access to environmental information.

Recognizing also¹¹ that every person has the right to live in an environment adequate to his or her health and well-being, and the duty, both individually and in association with others, to protect and improve the environment for the benefit of present and future generations,

Considering¹² that, to be able to assert this right and observe this duty, citizens must have access to information, be entitled to participate in decision-making

¹⁰ The UNECE is one of five regional commissions established under the jurisdiction of the UN Economic and Social Council. According to its Terms of reference and amongst other duties, the UNECE “shall initiate and participate in measures for facilitating concerted action for the economic development and integration of Europe, for raising the level of European economic activity, and for maintaining and strengthening the economic relations of the European countries both among themselves and with other countries of the world.” See: https://unece.org/DAM/oes/mandate/Commission_Rev5_English.pdf

¹¹ Underlined in the original version. See <https://unece.org/DAM/env/pp/documents/cep43e.pdf>

¹² *Idem*.

and have access to justice in environmental matters, and acknowledging in this regard that citizens may need assistance in order to exercise their rights,

Recognizing¹³ that, in the field of the environment, improved access to information and public participation in decision-making enhance the quality and the implementation of decisions, contribute to public awareness of environmental issues, give the public the opportunity to express its concerns and enable public authorities to take due account of such concerns.

Article 4. Access to environmental information

Each Party shall ensure that, subject to the following paragraphs of this article, public authorities, in response to a request for environmental information, make such information available to the public, within the framework of national legislation [...]

Aarhus Convention stresses the importance of the right of access to information, which considers an instrumental right to be able to live in a healthy environment and the obligation to preserve it.

3.1.2 A special consideration of scientific information

As seen in the previous subsection, the political spectrum of the right to access widens up due to the Open Data Directive and the Aarhus Convention, which create a direct link between the right to know and scientific studies. The right of citizens to promote their personal autonomy, to democratic participation, to transparency of public bodies, to find their representatives accountable and to combat corruption (UN, 2022), cannot be understood without access to scientific outcomes. Beyond the citizen empowerment that access to public information provides, accessing scientific information has an additional value due to the nature of scientific knowledge. As it is customary and of the essence of science, scientific outcomes must be able to be challenged by the scientific community. Using the Royal Society wording:

“Open inquiry is at the heart of the scientific enterprise. Publication of scientific theories - and of the experimental and observational data on which they are

¹³ *Idem.*

based - permits others to identify errors, to support, reject or refine theories and to reuse data for further understanding and knowledge. Science's powerful capacity for self-correction comes from this openness to scrutiny and challenge." (Royal Society, 2012, p. 7).

Consequently, access to scientific information does not only serve for the generic purposes obtained via a good normative framework to foster a better democratic system, but it also serves to extend in practice the value of the collective benefit driven by science, recognised as a fundamental right in articles 27 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, article 15 of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights and article 13 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union.

3.2 AS CLOSED AS NECESSARY

Once the norms and the reasons for the default "as open as possible" have been examined, it is necessary to analyse what exceptions may limit, either partially or totally, the openness of information. Similarly to knowledge openness, limiting its access is not a new issue adopted with the advent of the digital age, but has a long tradition. The creation of science as such represented the public spread of knowledge, contrary to the alchemical practice, having one of its first manifestations in 1665 when Oldenburg changed the convention at the Royal Society shifting from a secret log book to an open *Philosophical Transactions* journal (Johns, 2009, p. 61). The election of an open and public sharing of knowledge is rooted in scientific practices since its inception, and was meant to escape from secret performances.

The reasons to avoid the disclosure of information have been multiple, and their practice is widespread. Even in information technology and cybersecurity the "principle of least privilege (PoLP)" states that "Every program and every user of the system should operate using the least set of privileges necessary to complete the job" (Saltzer & Schroeder, 1975), emphasising the importance of controlled access to improve security, data protection and compliance. Nonetheless, closeness should have a reason and, when it comes to public information, according to the UN Report on Freedom of opinion and expression (UN, 2022, p. 6), the cause must be strict:

When restricting access to information, States must ensure that the restricting measure is in compliance with international human rights law [...] Secrecy laws should define national security limitations precisely and indicate clearly the criteria to be used in determining whether information can be appropriately declared non-disclosable on such grounds. [...] The right of access to information may also be restricted to protect the rights of others.

In the same spirit, the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science admits the existence of limits to openness. According to paragraph 8 of its text:

Access restrictions need to be proportionate and justified. They are only justifiable on the basis of the protection of human rights, national security, confidentiality, the right to privacy and respect for human subjects of study, legal process and public order, the protection of intellectual property rights, personal information, sacred and secret indigenous knowledge, and rare, threatened or endangered species.

Related to environmental information, the Aarhus Convention allows the restriction of the openness if the disclosure would adversely affect the following subject matter (Article 4.2):

- (a) The confidentiality of the proceedings of public authorities, where such confidentiality is provided for under national law;
- (b) International relations, national defence or public security;
- (c) The course of justice, the ability of a person to receive a fair trial or the ability of a public authority to conduct an enquiry of a criminal or disciplinary nature;
- (d) The confidentiality of commercial and industrial information, where such confidentiality is protected by law in order to protect a legitimate economic interest. Within this framework, information on emissions which is relevant for the protection of the environment shall be disclosed;
- (e) Intellectual property rights;
- (f) The confidentiality of personal data and/or files relating to a natural person where that person has not consented to the disclosure of the information to the public, where such confidentiality is provided for in national law;

- (g) The interests of a third party which has supplied the information requested without that party being under or capable of being put under a legal obligation to do so, and where that party does not consent to the release of the material; or
- (h) The environment to which the information relates, such as the breeding sites of rare species.

Finally, the European Open Data Directive includes a long list of factual situations where the holder of the information would be allowed to non-disclosure. They are enumerated in Article 1.2 of the Directive, which in summary and in what is relevant to this Deliverable, refer to documents “for which third parties hold intellectual property rights”, contain sensitive data on grounds of national security, defence, public security, statistical and commercial confidentiality, documents related to sensitive critical infrastructure, personal data, documents held by public service broadcasters, documents held by cultural establishments other than libraries, museums and archives. Referred to research data, Article 10 of the Directive mentions as limits intellectual property rights, personal data protection and confidentiality, security and legitimate commercial interests.

Table 1. Rationale for closedness

Source	Rationale
UNESCO Open Science Recommendation Paragraph 8	Protection of human rights, national security, confidentiality, the right to privacy and respect for human subjects of study, legal process and public order, the protection of intellectual property rights, personal information, sacred and secret indigenous knowledge, and rare, threatened or endangered species.
Aarhus Convention Article 4	<p>3. A request for environmental information may be refused if:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) The public authority to which the request is addressed does not hold the environmental information requested; (b) The request is manifestly unreasonable or formulated in too general a manner; or (c) The request concerns material in the course of completion or concerns internal communications of public authorities where such an exemption is provided for in national law or customary practice, taking into account the public interest served by disclosure. <p>4. A request for environmental information may be refused if</p>

Source	Rationale
	<p>the disclosure would adversely affect:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) The confidentiality of the proceedings of public authorities, where such confidentiality is provided for under national law; (b) International relations, national defence or public security; (c) The course of justice, the ability of a person to receive a fair trial or the ability of a public authority to conduct an enquiry of a criminal or disciplinary nature; (d) The confidentiality of commercial and industrial information, where such confidentiality is protected by law in order to protect a legitimate economic interest. Within this framework, information on emissions which is relevant for the protection of the environment shall be disclosed; (e) Intellectual property rights; (f) The confidentiality of personal data and/or files relating to a natural person where that person has not consented to the disclosure of the information to the public, where such confidentiality is provided for in national law; (g) The interests of a third party which has supplied the information requested without that party being under or capable of being put under a legal obligation to do so, and where that party does not consent to the release of the material; or (h) The environment to which the information relates, such as the breeding sites of rare species.
<p>Open Data Directive Article 1</p>	<p>2. This Directive does not apply to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (c) documents for which third parties hold intellectual property rights; (d) documents, such as sensitive data, which are excluded from access by virtue of the access regimes in the Member State, including on grounds of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) the protection of national security (namely, State security), defence, or public security; (ii) statistical confidentiality; (iii) commercial confidentiality (including business, professional or company secrets); (e) documents access to which is excluded or restricted on grounds of sensitive critical infrastructure protection related information as defined in point (d) of Article 2 of Directive 2008/114/EC;

Source	Rationale
	<p>(f) documents access to which is restricted by virtue of the access regimes in the Member States, including cases whereby citizens or legal entities have to prove a particular interest to obtain access to documents;</p> <p>(g) logos, crests and insignia;</p> <p>(h) documents, access to which is excluded or restricted by virtue of the access regimes on grounds of protection of personal data, and parts of documents accessible by virtue of those regimes which contain personal data the re-use of which has been defined by law as being incompatible with the law concerning the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data or as undermining the protection of privacy and the integrity of the individual, in particular in accordance with Union or national law regarding the protection of personal data;</p> <p>(i) documents held by public service broadcasters and their subsidiaries, and by other bodies or their subsidiaries for the fulfilment of a public service broadcasting remit;</p> <p>(j) documents held by cultural establishments other than libraries, including university libraries, museums and archives;</p> <p>(k) documents held by educational establishments of secondary level and below, and, in the case of all other educational establishments, documents other than those referred to in point (c) of paragraph 1;</p> <p>(l) documents other than those referred to in point (c) of paragraph 1 held by research performing organisations and research funding organisations, including organisations established for the transfer of research results.</p>
<p>Open Data Directive Article 10</p>	<p>1. [...] concerns relating to intellectual property rights, personal data protection and confidentiality, security and legitimate commercial interests, shall be taken into account in accordance with the principle of 'as open as possible, as closed as necessary'.</p>

Table number 1 shows the literal wording of the relevant part of the three texts (Unesco Recommendation on Open Science, Aarhus Convention and EU Open Data Directive), that contain the exceptions that limit the disclosure of information. The three texts offer different taxonomies of the limitations, to which two more may be added: The Royal Society (2012, pp. 44-59) proposed a taxonomy composed by three categories: (i) commercial interests and economic benefits, (ii) privacy and (iii) security and safety, while the OECD (2007, p. 16) proposed the following five: (i) national security, (ii) privacy

and confidentiality, (iii) trade secrets and intellectual property rights, (iv) protection of rare, threatened or endangered species and (v) data under consideration in legal actions. Furthermore, there are sector-specific reuse limitations (Graber-Soudry *et al.*, 2021, p. 47) which being so specific we do not include in this Deliverable, but which have to be taken into account in certain sectors.

Trying to find a common perspective applicable to the different limits, the diversity of the exceptions can, *ab initio*, be divided into two categories: The first category would refer to limitations due to the rights over the information, that is to say, due to externalities of the information. The second category would refer to limitations due to the content of the information, or, to express it in another way, to internalities of the information. The limitation due to the rights over the information will respond, in all cases, to a legal cause, while the limitation due to the informational content may be grounded on legal, social or ethical causes. It is also necessary to say that categories are not exclusive and one element may be included in one or more of them.

3.2.1 External limits: rights over the information

The external limits based on rights over the information means that an individual or an entity has the right to decide the conditions under which a third party may access, copy, modify, distribute or communicate publicly the information. The legal constructs that apply here are intellectual property, privacy, personality rights (voice, face) and the rights that a public body could exercise due to national or public security, which implies the right of a state to consider as secret an information:

- The rights may be incorporated by intellectual property laws, creating a copyrighted work, a patented invention, a trademark, a trade secret, a geographical indication or any other intellectual property field recognised in a jurisdiction. The applicability of exceptions or limitations to the intellectual property right will depend also on the jurisdiction, which may be one that abrogates for fair use (USA) or its equivalent fair dealing (UK, Australia, Canada, etc.) or for a taxative list of exceptions (also known as limitations) as in European Union. Furthermore, there is a diversity on the entering of a work into public domain, a period that also depends on the applicable jurisdiction.

- Privacy rights differ depending on the jurisdiction. The very well known General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)¹⁴ is only applicable in the European Union but other countries use similar approaches and equivalent protection.
- Personality rights refer to aspects of our body that belong to each individual, such as face or voice. They would protect against intrusions such as deep fakes or use of a similar voice without consent. Their recognition depends on the different jurisdictions.
- Finally, all public bodies have the right to secrecy due to legal causes as national or public security. Again, the diverse jurisdictions have their singular rules.

In the before mentioned rights, the rightholders are entitled to decide in an autonomous way the gradient of the extension of the openness/closedness. Thus, through licences or by way of agreement, conventions or factual public disclosure, the “closed as necessary” term may be shaped.

3.2.2 Internal limits: content of the information

3.2.2.1 Limits due to legal causes

Data or any other sort of information can be illegal due to its content. The reasons for the interdiction may come either from collective or individual values that the law deems worthy of protection. Regarding collective values, different examples that can be found across countries are national security, defence, public order, hate speech, blasphemy, sacred and secret indigenous knowledge. Referred to individual values, the examples are honour protection (interdiction of defamation), personality rights and privacy.

In these cases, the protection of the rights involved is of legal origin. Thus, these rights accomplish both internal and external limitations: the limitation comes from external causes to the content, there is a law that interdicts the openness of the data, but in these cases the interdiction is not because a third party is a rightholder of the information but due to the content of such data, which is deemed illegal *per se* by the law and which entice, in some cases, the exercise of the *ius puniendi* (the state’s right to punish criminal offenses).

¹⁴ See <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679>

Specific examples of these forbidden content would be instructions for weapon's production, military secrets, messages pushing for violence against a minority, offensive expression against religious values, pedophile images, disclosure of personal data without consent, use of a voice without consent and expressions against the honorability of a person. In these examples, the information is "closed as necessary" due to the subject matter, not due to rights over the data.

3.2.2.2 Limits due to social causes

Even though it may not exist a legal cause for not disclosing, disseminating or using certain data, there can exist situations where a community or group of individuals decide that some practices should be avoided or discontinued. A paradigmatic example may be found in the practice by digital image processing researchers of the use of Lenna's image. The Swedish model Lenna Forsén appeared in the Playboy magazine centerfold in its November 1972 issue. A group of researchers from the Signal and Image Processing Institute (SIPI) of the University of Southern California scanned part of the centerfold and used it for their image processing research (Hutchison, 2001). The picture was used world wide for research purposes until some voices discouraged its use due to inclusive values (Zug, 2015). Finally, while some academic journals have published editorials against its usage, proposing other pictures to be utilized instead of Lenna's image (Journal of Modern Optics Editorial, 2017; Nature Nanotech Editorial, 2018), the Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics has considered using this image as "potentially offensive material", "inconsistent with efforts to promote inclusion in mathematics, science, and engineering", not considering further submissions containing the image¹⁵.

Not all social limits may be based on values esteemed by a community. Section 4 of the White House Executive Order 14172 dated 20 January 2025 (USA, 2025), entitled "Restoring Names That Honor American Greatness", ordered the change of the name "Gulf of Mexico" into "Gulf of America". A side effect of this change was the new naming of the corresponding category in the Library of Congress Subject Headings¹⁶,

¹⁵ <https://epubs.siam.org/offensive-material>

¹⁶ <https://www.loc.gov/aba/publications/FreeLCSH/freelcsh.html>

perpetuating cataloging as what has been considered a “potent political instrument”¹⁷. In this case, the effects of the White House Executive Order are not legally binding outside United States’ jurisdiction, but have implications for all libraries around the world that use the Library of Congress cataloging system. Their decision here could be to move into another cataloguing system or not to update the categories.

Social limitations have no legal bases, although they may call to values already crystallized in legal norms. By their nature, social limitations are dynamic, they change according to time and territory, and cannot be anticipated. Their existence outside the law does not mean they are of minor importance, as their influence in a society may lead to legal changes, as it happened after Alan Turing’s suicide and the decriminalisation of prostitution and same sex relationships, as studied by UK Parliament in the well known Wolfenden Report (1957)¹⁸ or as legal changes have happened after activist efforts and civil disobedience.

In such cases, the “as closed as necessary” terms are applicable due to a collective convention for not using the data. If the information is used, there is no legal infringement, but there may be a social penalty.

3.2.2.3 Limits due to ethical principles

Finally, the last category related to “as closed as necessary” relates to ethical causes, which in many cases are not distinguishable from the social reasons as the social movements respond in many cases to ethical principles. A literature review shows a wide set of texts regarding research ethics, being the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity or All European Academies (ALLEA) one of its best examples (ALLEA, 2023). According to this text,

Failing to follow good research practices violates professional responsibilities. It damages the research processes, degrades relationships among researchers, undermines trust in and the credibility of research, wastes resources, and may

¹⁷ <https://www.llrx.com/2025/04/classification-as-colonization-the-hidden-politics-of-library-catalogs/>

¹⁸ https://www.humandignitytrust.org/wp-content/uploads/resources/Wolfenden_Report_1957.pdf

expose research participants and subjects, users, society, or the environment to unnecessary harm.

Following ALLEA Code of Conduct, the following behaviours constitute an infringement of ethical values:

Research misconduct is traditionally defined as fabrication, falsification, or plagiarism (the so-called FFP categorisation) in proposing, performing, or reviewing research, or in reporting research results:

- Fabrication is making up data or results and recording them as if they were real.
- Falsification is manipulating research materials, equipment, images, or processes, or changing, omitting, or suppressing data or results without justification.
- Plagiarism is using other people's work or ideas¹⁹ without giving proper credit to the original source.

Scientists may consider that certain scholarly publications or data research could have a dubious source, which may lead to retraction. Fabrication, falsification and plagiarism (which is also a legal limit) may lead to decisions not to use the information. Data that comes from dubious origins, such as paper mills or scientific activities whose purpose would not be approved by ethical committees (embryo cloning, etc.) falls under this category.

ALLEAs' text does not limit the research misconduct to the three above practices, and includes other ones which it deems unacceptable. From the conducts contained therein, the following ones have relationship with research outcomes or data: Hiding the use of AI or automated tools in the creation of content or drafting of publications, withholding research data or results without justification, citing selectively or inaccurately and misrepresenting research achievements, data, involvement, or interests. As stated

¹⁹ We strongly disagree with the inclusion of ideas inside the plagiarism category. Ideas are free, and not protected under the copyright moral right of attribution. When ideas are formalized in a work, then it is the work what is protected, but not the ideas. For example the idea that a woman loves a man, a man loves the woman but their families do not agree with the relationship, has been extensively used in myriads of works. Not to recognise third parties ideas is not plagiarism, it is intellectual dishonesty.

before, there is a wide amount of literature regarding ethical principles which can be used as a limitation of the openness of information, although we limit our analysis to ALLEA's document due to its relevance and to its European scope.

3.3 CATEGORIES PROPOSAL

Summarising this section, this deliverable proposes in Table 2 a taxonomy of the “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” applicable terms, which may be used as a basis for future closed vocabularies developments over the existing ones, summarized by FAIR-Impact project in section 4 of its D6.2 - Core metadata schema for legal interoperability (Rouchon *et al*, 2024). The taxonomy is presented in both table and image format.

Table 2. Summary of the proposed categories of opened/closed

Open (Property: Open by default)				
Closed (Property: Exception)	External limits (due to rights over the data)	Intellectual property rights	Copyright	Moral rights <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Attribution - Integrity of the work - Right to remain anonymous - Use of pseudonym (Bansky, for example) or a sign.
				Exclusive rights (forbidden activities unless there is permission, the use is under an exception, or the work is under public domain): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To copy - To make derivative copies - To distribute (tangible copies) - To communicate to the public (intangible copies)
				Only for databases: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Sui generis</i> right
			Patents Trademarks Trade secrets Geographical indications	
		Privacy rights		

		Personality rights		
		Right to secrecy		
	Internal limits (due to the content of the data)	Legal causes	Based on collective values	National security Defence Public order Hate speech Blasphemy Sacred and secret indigenous knowledge
			Based in individual values	Honour protection (interdiction of defamation) Personality rights Privacy
		Social causes (based on an agreement of a community)		
		Ethical causes	Fabricated data False data Plagiarism	

Image 1. Summary of the proposed categories of opened/closed

(Credit: Hans-Jürgen Wolf, based on a table by Javier de la Cueva)

4 FAIR GUIDING PRINCIPLES

Having explained the legal, social and ethical conundrums applicable to the opposition open/closed data, this section will study how they can interfere with each of the components of the FAIR guiding principles. Not all the principles are subject to intrusiveness with the same intensity, nor equal interference may be caused to data than to its metadata. Therefore, it is necessary to analyse the 15 subitems of the guiding principles. Quoting Wilkinson *et al.* (2016):

Moreover, the modularity of the Principles, and their distinction between data and metadata, explicitly support a wide range of special circumstances. One such example is highly sensitive or personally-identifiable data, where publication of rich metadata to facilitate discovery, including clear rules regarding the process for accessing the data, provides a high degree of 'FAIRness' even in the absence of FAIR publication of the data itself. A second example involves the publication of non-data research objects. Analytical workflows, for example, are a critical component of the scholarly ecosystem, and their formal publication is necessary to achieve both transparency and scientific reproducibility. The FAIR principles can equally be applied to these non-data assets, which need to be identified, described, discovered, and reused in much the same manner as data.

The distinction is important: data (including, more specifically, digital objects and research outputs) may be FAIR even though its content is not available publicly: FAIR data does not mean open data.

It is also relevant to describe what is understood by the terms "data" and "metadata". In this deliverable, we use the approach followed in the *EOSC interoperability framework: report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Groups FAIR and Architecture* (European Commission, 2021, p. 8):

We also use the term metadata widely. For this, we have decided to choose the ISO11179 definition of metadata, which defines it as "descriptive data about an object". That is, metadata is a kind of data: data may act as metadata when the descriptive relationship is revealed between the data (now metadata) and the target object(s). And metadata that is the same for more than one object is metadata for a

class of objects...” (ISO/IEC CD 111791)²⁰. This definition also aligns well with the definition used in the paper on the FAIR Principles, which states that the term “data” is used to refer to all types of digital resources (not just data in the restricted sense, but also, for example, software, workflows, hardware designs, etc.) and metadata is any description of a resource that can serve the purpose of enabling findability and/or reusability and/or interpretation and/or assessment of that resource.

In summary, using laypeople’s terms and in search of a simple explanation understandable by everybody, in the following subsections the term data will refer to any sort of information, while the term metadata will be the description of such data: its language, who collected the data, who authorised the collection, who financed it, what is the data about, who are the different authors, what is its size, format, provenance... This differentiation means that for the 15 guiding principles and its tension with sensitive data, two layers have to be taken into account, data and metadata. Regarding data, singular cases have to be studied separately. Regarding metadata, Table 3 shows recommendations of information which inclusion should be avoided.

Table 3. Recommendations for metadata.

<p>External limits. Rights over the content.</p>	<p>Metadata should not include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Terms or expressions that could infringe IPRs - Characters that would reveal third parties private data, such as national ID or passport number, dates of birth, biometrics, ethnicity, religion, political affiliation, financial information... - Personal characteristics of third parties. - Secret items such as formulas, latitude/longitude of sensitive emplacements (strategic premises, military...).
<p>Internal limits. Nature of the informational content.</p>	<p>Metadata should not include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National security information - Defence information - Public order information - Hate speech - Blasphemy - Sacred and secret indigenous knowledge

²⁰ <https://www.iso.org/standard/78914.html>

4.1 TO BE FINDABLE

Regarding the Findable principle, none of the four sub-items of this item implies the access to the content of the information. What is relevant for this principle is the possibility to find the data, not to access it. Therefore, its tension capacity between FAIR principles and sensitive data is minor as there is no data involved and only metadata. Notwithstanding, the importance of metadata as an intrusive factor is evident in cases such as criminal records: the mere existence of a person’s criminal record, even though the access to the data content is not provided, has a significant meaning. The same assertion is applicable to all other cases where the inclusion of a person in a database would carry, *per se*, qualitative information: health, debtor, public benefits databases, etc.

To summarise up, when dealing properly with metadata, the Findable element may be accomplished with no tension with sensitive data.

F1. (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier

- Metadata: Description of the data should follow table 3 recommendation, avoiding the usage of “as closed as necessary” elements.
- Data is not accessed.

F2. data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)

- Metadata: Description of the data should follow table 3 recommendation. The metadata richness should avoid the usage of “as closed as necessary” elements.
- Data is merely described, not accessed.

F3. metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes

- Metadata: Description of the data should follow table 3 recommendation, avoiding the usage of “as closed as necessary” elements.
- Data is merely described, not accessed.

F4. (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

- Metadata: Description of the data should follow table 3 recommendation, avoiding the usage of “as closed as necessary” elements.
- Data: the registry or indexing of the data should be done through the registry or indexing of its metadata. Registry or indexing of the data should be dependent and follow the same conditions set forth in the To be Accessible principle.

4.2 TO BE ACCESSIBLE

Accessibility provides maximum tension between the principles and sensitive data, as this principle refers to the disclosure of the content of such data.

A1. (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol

- Metadata: Description of the data should follow table 3 recommendation, avoiding the usage of “as closed as necessary” elements.
- Data: As long as the content of the data is not accessed (although the PID points to the dataset), this item does not affect the tension, as it is merely an instrumental principle. In this case, the authentication and authorisation conditions are crucial.
- Instrumental: The openness of the data will depend on the openness of the standardised communications protocol. Proprietary protocols should be avoided.

A1.1 the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable

- Metadata: Not applicable to metadata.
- Data: Not applicable to data.
- Instrumental: Free is an ambiguous term, as it may refer to price or to permissions to exercise activities regulated by IPR. The openness of the data will depend on the openness, freedom and implementability of the protocol.

A1.2 the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary

- Metadata: Not applicable to metadata.
- Data: Not applicable to data.
- Instrumental: The existence of an authentication and authorization procedure is critical for managing the tension between the FAIR principles and sensitive data.

A2. metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available

- Metadata: Description of the data should follow table 3 recommendation, avoiding the usage of “as closed as necessary” elements.
- Data: Not applicable to data.

4.3 To be INTEROPERABLE

The interoperability refers to four layers: technical, semantic, organisational and legal. While technical interoperability refers to the “ability of different information technology systems and software applications to communicate and exchange data” (European Commission, 2021, p. 11), semantic interoperability makes reference to the “the ability of computer systems to transmit data with unambiguous, shared meaning” (Lehväslaiho *et al*, 2019). Hence, interoperability lays on the ability to do an action, supplying the possibilities to make possible the consequences of such action. In this case, the action relates to sharing data between machines, therefore, the tension will depend on the data that is *effectively* shared, which in turn depends on the To be Accessible principle.

I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.

- Metadata: Description of the data should follow table 3 recommendation, avoiding the usage of “as closed as necessary” elements.
- Data: The IPR of the language used and of the knowledge representation may hinder the openness of the data.

I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles

- Metadata: Description of the data should follow table 3 recommendation, avoiding the usage of “as closed as necessary” elements.
- Data: If data itself uses a vocabulary that follows the FAIR principles, it should also take table 3 recommendation into account.
- Vocabulary: The vocabulary should follow table 3 recommendation, avoiding the usage of “as closed as necessary” elements. Notwithstanding, it may be necessary (for example in the hypothetical construction of a list of forbidden terms) that they should necessarily be included in the list). Special attention should be taken in this case.

I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

- Metadata: Description of the data should follow table 3 recommendation, avoiding the usage of “as closed as necessary” elements.
- Data: not applicable, although there could be cases where qualified references may increase the predictability of sensitive data, even though it is not openly accessible.

4.4 TO BE REUSABLE

Reusability of the data produces maximum tension between the principles and sensitive data, as this principle refers to the activities of sharing the content of such data. In this case, this parameter does not depend on the To be Accessible principle, because it takes it for granted. No possible reusability can exist if no accessibility has been already executed.

R1. meta(data) are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes

- Metadata: Description of the data should follow table 3 recommendation, avoiding the usage of “as closed as necessary” elements.
- Data: Data is reused. Thus, potentially there is maximum tension, which will depend on the nature of the original data.

R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license

- Metadata: Description of the data should follow table 3 recommendation, avoiding the usage of “as closed as necessary” elements.
- Data: Even though the licence may not be necessary for certain data, as when it refers to factual information (example: temperatures) a licence may be needed due to the database *sui generis* right. The licence will not affect the tension between the FAIR principles and the sensitive data when sensitiveness is due to the content of the information and not the rights over it.

R1.2. (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance

- Metadata: Description of the data should follow table 3 recommendation, avoiding the usage of “as closed as necessary” elements.
- Data: Data *per se* will not include detailed provenance.

- Detailed provenance may allow traceability of the reuse permissions, if they are not already present, contributing to a better understanding of the possible tension. Special precautions should be taken in case of the possibilities of using provenance metadata to connect the data with other external sources of information.

R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

- Metadata: Description of the data should follow table 3 recommendation, avoiding the usage of “as closed as necessary” elements
- Data: Tension will depend on the domain-relevant community standards.
- Domain-relevant community standards. If they include “as closed as necessary” items, an alteration or completion of the standards should be studied and, as the case may be, proposed to the community.

5 APPLICATION TO SIESTA USE CASES

Regarding how the before study could be applicable to SIESTA's use cases, they do not differ from any other scientific or technical discipline regarding the applicability of the expression "as open as possible, as closed as necessary". During the SIESTA project, WP5 has closely followed the activities held in the use cases WP, namely WP 14, 15, 17 and 18, and it has found that there exist singularities applicable to each of the different realms. But even though each case should be studied particularly, the proceeding on how to apply these rules to each of SIESTA's use cases would include the following common steps:

- Identify the existence of potential issues with the data, checking thoroughly each of the items contained in Table 2.
- Check how the potential issues may affect the guiding principles regarding both metadata and data.
- Apply a correction based on the nature of the potential issue (personal data should receive an anonymization process, metadata about personal data should be checked if it could imply deanonymization, moral right should receive attribution, data should receive a liberal intellectual property licence, etc.).

The result of the analysis should be integrated into the DMP, as it includes relevant items that merit their inclusion in such a document. SIESTA's DMP is published in ARGOS, which produces automatic access in ZENODO, being able in this way to provide examples useful for the research community.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable has covered an analytical approach to the expression “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”, proposing jurisdiction agnostic categories and how they can be applied to the 15 guiding principles so this mapping could be useful for SIESTA use cases’ researchers and the research community in general. The followed method can serve as a guidance for scientists who need a wide approach to the tension created by the opposition open/closed, and under a global perspective.

Regarding further steps, the conceptual analysis provided in this deliverable may be enriched by documenting practical experiences.

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